

DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING PRONUNCIATION

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Annotation: This article discusses the concept of pronunciation, the meaning of pronunciation and its importance in learning foreign languages.

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Objectively deciding how to present a pronunciation unit alone, in a word, or in a sentence, in observation of pronunciation skills. When teaching pronunciation, introducing many students to a pronunciation unit depends on knowing the methodical explanation of the item. Introduction means the pronunciation of the phonetic unit by the teacher and the participation of the students. The three methods have their own development and support aspects. In teaching pronunciation of a foreign language in Uzbek schools, the teacher works from the general to the specific, and the student moves from the specific to the general is the optimal methodical way proven by experience. "Pronunciation" refers to the way in which we make the sound of words. To pronounce words, we push air from our lungs up through our throat and vocal cords, through our mouth, past our tongue and out between our teeth and lips. To change the sound that we are making, we mainly use the muscles of our mouth, tongue and lips to control the shape of our mouth and the flow of air. There are three ways to present pronunciation in a foreign language: speaking alone, in words and sentences, and listening. Pronunciation teaching methods are related to the ease/difficulty level of the sound. For example, from the perspective of the learner's mother tongue (or language experience), similar, close, dissimilar units can be distinguished. Vowels and consonants spoken alone are extremely difficult, vowels and consonants spoken in words are of moderate difficulty, and vowels and consonants spoken in sentences form easy phonetic units. Teaching the pronunciation of a new sound, which is considered difficult, goes through the following educational stages.

1. Speaking of the speech sample performed by the teacher and listening stage by the students. Students' attention is focused on understanding the content of the sentence and the meaning of the new word in it. The teacher says the new sound, first in a sentence, then in a word, and the students understand it by listening.

2. From synthetic (whole) perception of the phonetic unit to analytical (in parts) listening. The teacher distinguishes the new sound in the word and briefly explains its

articulation, that is, he gives a short rule-instruction. (Pronunciation rules are explained below.) According to the teacher's instructions, students prepare their speech organs to pronounce this sound. The teacher's pronunciation and explanations help with this. The second stage of preparation for saying the sound out loud ensures that it is said in internal speech.

3. The stage of transition from auditory perception and internal speech to pronunciation. The teacher shows the new sound pattern, the students repeat it together and individually. Thus, the pronunciation of a new sound in isolation is learned through analysis and imitation.

4. The stage of saying a new sound in combination with others. The sound is pronounced in combinations with learned sounds. Vowel and consonant combinations are practiced as much as possible.

5. A new sound is pronounced in the word. Following the example of the teacher, the students pronounce in chorus and individually. If there are two new sounds in the word Mabodo, first of all, they are thoroughly mastered, and then the second one is pronounced (following the criterion of distributing difficulties). At the end, the word is pronounced. This stage is dedicated to teaching the meaning of sound (phoneme).

6. Now the new sound is pronounced in the sentence. The teacher starts, the students stop imitating. The expression of sound and meaning of the word is formed directly in the sentence. At this stage, speaking sentences means practicing at the level of information exchange.

7. The stage of strengthening the newly acquired sound. The studied sound is freely used in different pronunciation situations, that is, in small and large contexts, as well as alone, in words and sentences.

8. Exercises should be performed so that students do not confuse the new sound with the existing sounds in the language experience (such as comparison with the sound of the mother tongue and the second language and comparison with the sounds of the foreign language previously acquired). Comparing and contrasting is practiced on the basis of sounds alone, in words and in sentences. In this final stage, exercises are performed under the guidance of the teacher.

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